

Organo-antimony Compounds. Part II. The Constitution of *p*-Aminostibinic Acid and its Amine Salts.

By SUDHIR CHANDRA NIYOGY.

The preparation of aromatic antimonials is now invariably carried out by the replacement of a diazo complex by antimonious acid in a suitable form and in an alkaline medium. In the event of the compound to be 'stibinated' containing a nitro group, the reaction medium is to be maintained almost neutral or even faintly acid to avoid undesirable side reactions (D.R.P. 254421). Previous attempts to stibinate aromatic compounds by the well known Bechamp condensation were unsuccessful and the statement that aniline when heated with antimony trichloride gave rise to *p*-amino stibonous chloride (Breinl and Nierenstein, *Ann. Tropical Medicine & Parasit.*, 1908, 21, 379) proved to be erroneous (May, "The Chemistry of Synthetic Drugs," p. 215). The only remaining source of the aryl stibinic acids (previous to the discovery of the diazo reaction mentioned above) was the triaryl stibines and its dihalides and by their careful and progressive dearylation, a number of derivatives of phenyl and *p*-tolyl series were obtained. This process of dearylation was frequently accompanied by changes in which the bond between carbon and antimony was ruptured and the expected degradation product could not be isolated.

Although a number of patents has been taken out to cover the preparation of the various stibinic acids, the mechanism of the reaction does not appear to have been completely studied. Schmidt (*Annalen*, 1920, 421, 174) suggested that antimony oxide in order to take part in the reaction, must be in its hydrated form *i.e.*, as antimonious acid, which is capable of existence in tautomeric forms represented by the following:—

(1)

(2)

In the first antimony is trivalent and in the second pentavalent. The reaction, according to D. R. P. 254421, takes place between the diazo salts and antimonious acids. If it is assumed that a molecule of HX is eliminated in the first stage forming a diazo antimonial, which subsequently loses nitrogen, the course of the reaction may be represented as follows —

A compound of the type of $\text{Ar O Sb}(\text{OH})_2$, which would be expected according to the first scheme, would be an aryl ester of antimonious acid and as such extremely unstable and would be at once hydrolysed into phenol and antimonious acid (Mackey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 604). So it is necessary to assume that antimony oxide reacts in the pentavalent form, if there is an elimination of HX in the first stage. But the reaction can also be looked upon from another standpoint. Trivalent antimony compounds always exhibit a great tendency to pass to pentavalent forms. The action therefore can very easily be explained as follows —

To settle this question it is necessary to study another series of reactions. May (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1037) during his study

of the action of diazonium chlorides on antimony trichlorides noticed that these two substances in acid solution gave rise to stable crystalline insoluble additive compounds, which can be kept in the dry state without any risk of explosion. It is possible to arrive at a definite conclusion as to whether the antimony reacts in the trivalent or pentavalent form, from a study of these additive compounds:—

It thus appears that the probability of the antimony reacting in the trivalent form is greater than that of its reacting in the pentavalent condition.

The yield of aryl stibinic acid prepared by the diazo reaction leaves much to be desired. It is found that during the process of the elimination of nitrogen, dark coloured bye-products and reduction products are always obtained. The latter consists of a compound in which the diazo complex has been replaced by hydrogen. With careful regulation of the reaction this can be controlled to a considerable extent. It is well known that the replacement of a diazo-group takes place through the *syn*-diazo form while its reduction involves the *anti*-configuration. Since the conversion of *syn*- to *anti*-configuration is markedly influenced by the alkalinity of the reaction medium, it is of the utmost importance that this should be carefully regulated, if the reduction process is to be kept to a minimum. In general, in applying this reaction, the reaction medium may be kept more alkaline than in the case of the corresponding arsenicals.

The nature of the aryl stibinic acid is a matter of controversy. Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 697) maintains that they are complex in character as in the following $(\text{ArSbO}_3\text{H}_2)_2$, which may also be written as $\{(3 \text{ ArSbO}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}\}2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ because it is found that two molecules of water can be easily removed in a vacuum desiccator while the remaining molecule is very firmly attached to the molecule. In their behaviour towards alkali, aryl stibinic acids

show some peculiarities, from which Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) concludes that they are complex in character. Macallum (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, **42**, 468T) on the other hand, as the result of molecular weight determinations by the cryoscopic method, has come to the conclusion that they are simple molecules, ArSbO_3H_3 . Turning now to the salts of the aryl stibinic acid, it is found that the nature of alkali used for preparing them, plays an important part. According to Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) sodium and potassium hydroxides finally bring about the dissociation of the complex molecules into its simplest form but with lithium hydroxide two molecules of the stibinic acid remain associated together even after complete neutralisation. The complex nature of the acids is also supported by the analysis of the alkali salts. Farghar and Gray (*J. Pharm. & Expt. Therap.*, 1921, **18**, 353) have found that in all samples analysed by them, the atomic ratio of alkali metal to antimony is almost 1:3. Dunning and Reid, however, have found in a recent work (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2959; 1927, **49**, 2869) that some azo derivatives of *p*-aminophenyl stibinic acid gave the disodium salts.

This result is rather remarkable, when it is remembered that no previous worker had been able to prepare salts in which the atomic ratio of sodium to antimony is 2:1. The present work was undertaken to settle this question finally. It has been found that aryl stibinic acids are capable of forming salts with primary, secondary, and tertiary amines. These amines are certainly weaker than sodium or potassium hydroxide, so that the dissociation of the complex molecule will not take place. Finally molecular weight determination of these amine salts ought to settle the question once for all. But unfortunately, the latter portion of the work could not be carried out as the amine salts form a clear solution in water which, however, gives rise to a white precipitate on standing. The analytical results obtained show that in every case there are 3 molecules of the stibinic acid to one molecule of the base, thus supporting Schmidt's contention.

The preparation of the starting material, *p*-aminophenyl stibinic acid, has been described by various workers (U. S. P. 1260707, D.R.P. 254121, E.P. 10350 (1912); and also Dunning and Reid, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2959; 1927, **49**, 2869). But an unexpected result was obtained in the course of this work. The usual process consists of two stages:—(1) Treating a diazotised solution

of acetyl *p*-phenylene diamine with antimony trichloride in hydrochloric acid solution to obtain an additive compound and the decomposition of the same with dilute caustic soda to obtain 4-acetylaminophenyl stibinic acid; (2) hydrolysis of acetyl group with caustic soda solution. In one experiment, the additive compound described above was left to dry in a vacuum desiccator over soda-lime, as the mass was very slightly acid. On subsequent treatment with caustic soda solution it was found that the product was not 4-acetylaminophenyl stibinic acid but 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. The alkaline hydrolysis of the acetyl group takes considerable time for completion and thus a great speeding up of the reaction is possible by leaving the faintly acid additive compound in a desiccator.

For the preparation of the amine salts it was found essential that the 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid should be in the highest state of purity attainable. Repeated washing with distilled water failed to effect the complete purification. The crude acid was converted into the hydrochloride of the stibinic chloride $\text{SbCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$ by treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid. When decomposed with the calculated quantity of caustic soda, the chloride yielded the free acid, which after repeated washing, was in a sufficiently pure state for the next operation. The purified acid was then suspended in water and an aqueous or alcoholic solution of the base was added drop by drop, till the whole went into solution. The solution was then heated on a water-bath for some time, filtered from any precipitates and rectified spirit was added in excess when the salt separated out.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of p-Aminophenyl Stibinic Acid.—Acetyl *p*-phenylene diamine (100 g.) was added to water (300 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (37%, 100 c.c.). A portion of the hydrochloride separated out. The whole was then cooled to 0° with crushed ice and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (50 g.). After diazotisation, hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was further added. To this solution was gradually added, with stirring, a solution of antimony trichloride prepared by dissolving antimony trioxide (70 g.) in hydrochloric acid (250 c.c.). An almost colourless crystalline precipitate, immediately separated which was filtered, washed first with dilute hydrochloric acid and

then with water to remove hydrochloric acid. It was found that the wash water was very slightly acid. The moist mass was then left to dry in a vacuum desiccator over soda-lime for 48 hours. When opened, it was found that the mass was still somewhat moist: yield—250 g.

25 Gm. of the moist mass was beaten up with water (100-125 c.c.) and cooled with cracked ice to 0-5°. Caustic soda solution (8 gm.) in 50-60 c.c. of water was gradually added with vigorous stirring. The evolution of nitrogen ceased in about 30 minutes. The alkaline solution was then almost neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid, saturated with carbon dioxide for 30 minutes and filtered. The clear filtrate, on acidifying with dilute acetic acid, gave a colourless gelatinous precipitate which was found to be soluble in dilute mineral acids. The solution in mineral acids also gave the usual diazo reaction. Thus it was concluded that the precipitate was not 4-acetylaminophenyl stibinic acid but 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. The precipitated stibinic acid was then filtered, washed repeatedly with distilled water to remove inorganic impurities and then dissolved in conc. hydrochloric acid and precipitated with the required quantity of caustic soda solution. This was again filtered off washed with distilled water and suspended in water. As 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid decomposes very easily in the dry state, it cannot be preserved in a dry condition and should always be kept suspended in water or as its alkali salt.

To the suspension of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid in water, was gradually added a solution of methylamine in water, till the whole went into solution. The clear red solution was then heated on a water-bath for about 5 minutes. A gelatinous precipitate generally separates which was filtered off and to the clear filtrate a large excess of rectified spirit was added. A white or very slightly coloured precipitate separated which was allowed to stand overnight, filtered, washed with rectified spirit and then with absolute alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride. (Found: C, 27.48; H, 3.23; Sb, 45.1. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_2\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ requires C, 28.04; H, 3.5; Sb, 44.2 per cent.).

The preparation of the other salts was carried out in exactly the same way, taking care not to heat the solution of the stibinic acid above 80° or for a long time.

Dimethylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 27.8; H, 4.4; Sb, 43.4. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_2\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ requires C, 28.8, H, 3.7, Sb, 43.1 per cent.).

Trimethylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 29.1; H, 3.02; Sb, 42.9. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ requires C, 29.8; H, 2.9; Sb, 42.6 per cent.)

Ethylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 27.6; H, 4.23; Sb, 42.8. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ requires C, 28.8; H, 3.7; Sb, 43.4 per cent.)

Diethylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 29.8; H, 3.84; Sb, 41.9. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{NH}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ requires C, 30.7; H, 4.07; Sb, 42.6 per cent.)

Triethylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 33.21; H, 3.95; Sb, 39.4. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ requires C, 32.4; H, 4.4; Sb, 40.54 per cent.)

Propylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 29.1; H, 3.7; Sb, 43.2. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ requires C, 29.8; H, 3.2; Sb, 42.6 per cent.)

isoAmylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 32.2; H, 4.38; Sb, 40.6. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ requires C, 31.6; H, 3.84; Sb, 41.2 per cent.)

Allylamine Salt.—(Found: C, 29.07; H, 4.2; Sb, 42.3. $(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2)_3\text{CH}_2 : \text{CH}, \text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$ requires C, 29.88; H, 3.66; Sb, 42.7 per cent.)

Properties.—All these amine salts are almost colourless amorphous solids having no definite melting point. They dissolve freely in water forming a clear red solution which in a few minutes turns opaque due to the separation of a white precipitate. Moist air and atmospheric carbon dioxide cause some decomposition in them, as when thus exposed they are no longer soluble in water. They are insoluble in all organic solvents except glycerine, in which they dissolve on heating and can be precipitated by adding alcohol.

I desire to express my thanks to Prof. H. K. Sen, for the kind interest he has taken in this work and also to Mr. Kshitish Chandra Bose-Ray for having helped me in the analytical portion of the work.

